

(The gathering of the Messenger of God does not falter) وجمع رسول الله لا يتشعث

also known as "The Ishriniya Organization."

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Entry tags: Islamic Traditions, Sufism, Tijāniyyah, Religious Group

The gathering of the Messenger of God does not falter (Wa jam'u Rasulullah la yata sha'asu) was a union of Islam adherents that usually congregate to chant praises to the Prophet Muhammad (peace be upon him) based on some stanzas prepared by Abdurrahman ibn Yakhliphan titled "Divan means accepted in praising the Prophet, may God bless him and grant him peace" the group was earlier established under the chieftainship of the late Malam Bala mai Yafe in the Kano state, from which the branches of the union were extended to other States of northern Nigeria, where the group members congregate on either daily or weekly bases to chant the stanzas of the book which most of the members commit the stanzas into their memory, while others relied on the book to read the stanzas.

Date Range: 1793 BCE - 1864 CE

Region: Sokoto

Region tags: Africa, Western Africa, Benin, Burkina Faso, Niger, Togo, Nigeria, Chad, Cameroon

Sokoto around 1870, during the reign of Ahmadu Rufai. Adapted from AbdurRahman AbdulMoneim [https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_\(cropped\).png](https://commons.wikimedia.org/wiki/File:Sokoto_Sultanate_(cropped).png)

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: محمد غبريم بن محمد الداغري (2003). النوافح العطرية المختصرة من النفحة العنبرية في حل ألفاظ العشرينية في مدح خير البرية صلى الله عليه وسلم. دار الكتب العلمية

Online sources for understanding this subject:

— Source 1 URL: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=671WLyPh5qo>

— Source 1 Description: Nasara Hausa (2019). Bala mai Yafe Ishiriniya.

— Source 2 URL: <https://archive.org/details/Ishriniyya/Ishriniyya%20%281%29/>

— Source 2 Description: للفازاوي (2019) الديوان وسائل المتقبله في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

— Source 1 URL: https://www.noor-book.com/book/internal_download/807c8c08cf66db48ea3b08c7e4c73443a96c62d2/2/114345834f7f541c69a4a9eb8b9

— Source 1 Description: عبد الرحمن ابن يخلفتن (2017). ديوان الوسائل المتقبله في مدح النبي صلى الله عليه وسلم. المطبعة الأدبية

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Notes: Many religious groups are in contact with the religion of Islam apart from this group.

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Notes: New members are contentiously invited to the group.

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Notes: Membership to the group is not assigned by birth.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Notes: Membership is by personal choice.

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Notes: Members of the group are assigned by class.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

Notes: The group recruits children, young and old aged people.

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Notes: The group is meant for both male and female sexes.

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

Notes: Members attend congregational chanting of the poem book (Ishiriniyyah).

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– Yes [specify]: Educational capability of reading the book.

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Notes: The group recruits new members among the adherents of Islam.

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Notes: The group does not consider exiting the movement as a form of apostasy.

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Estimated population, numeric: 1060000

Notes: Members of the group are found within the nineteen states of northern Nigeria.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Estimated population, percentage of sample region: 1.5

Notes: The population of northern Nigeria is said to have reached 160 million, while members of the group members were estimated to have reached 1060000.

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Large official religious group with smaller religious groups also openly allowed

Notes: The religious group's members are known to adhere to the Islamic religion, so they mingle openly with followers of other groups.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: It is a well-known organization with an administrative structure.

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Notes: The people in the group saw Al-Wasa'il Mutaqabbilah as a book of adoration for the Prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Notes: The group does not have a monumental building of worship.

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Notes: The group does not have iconography.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Notes: The group believed in spirit-body distinction, as the spirit continues life after the decay of its dead body.

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Notes: The spirit mind has the power to move freely after the sleep of its body, which leads to the experiences of dreams.

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The group believed in the afterlife, as analyzed by Islamic principles.

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– No

Notes: The location of the afterlife is only known by God.

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Notes: The group rejected reincarnation in this world on the principles of Islam.

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Notes: There is no special treatment for the corpse of the group members apart from that of Islam.

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Notes: Co-sacrifice is prohibited in the principles of the group.

Are grave goods present:

– No

Notes: No good is allowed to accompany corpse burial apart from the simple shroud.

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Notes: Dead members of the group are buried on the principles of Islam.

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

Notes: The group rejected cenotaphs on the directives of Islam.

↳ In cemetery:

– Yes

Notes: Group members are buried in the cemetery.

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Notes: The group did not believe in a family tomb.

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Notes: Domestic individuals are taken to the cemetery.

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believed in supernatural beings.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believed in the existence of the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– No

Notes: The nature of the supreme high God is beyond human comprehension.

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme high God is the sky deity.

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Notes: The Supreme High God is not confined to the underworld but is fully aware of everything happening (in the world).

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Notes: Monarchs are servants of the high god.

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The monarch is not seen as an embodiment of the high god.

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Notes: The supreme high god is not having a keen relationship with the elites.

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural high God is unquestionably good.

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: He creates and controls creatures.

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural High God knows everything in the world.

- ↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
– No
Notes: Knowledge of the Supernatural High God has no restriction on human affairs.
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
– No
Notes: There is no restriction to the knowledge of the supernatural high God within the sample region.
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:
– Yes
Notes: Knowledge of the supernatural high God has no restriction within the sample region.
- ↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Yes
Notes: Knowledge of the high God has no restriction outside the sample region.
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural High God can see everywhere.
- ↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Yes
Notes: Darkness does not cover anything from his sight.
- ↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural High God sees what is hidden in the mind.
- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural High God knows the characters of humans.
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
– Yes
Notes: Supreme High God knows what will happen in the future.

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
– Yes [specify]: Supernatural High God has an entire knowledge of this world.

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: Supernatural High God has deliberate causal efficacy in the world.

↳ The supreme high god can reward:
– Yes
Notes: Supreme High God rewards the proper activities of humans.

↳ The supreme high god can punish:
– Yes
Notes: The supreme high God punishes evil doers in the hereafter.

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
– Yes
Notes: The power of the supreme high God causes everything in the world.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
– Yes
Notes: His emotions are not visible to humans.

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
– Yes
Notes: Negative emotions of the supreme high God cannot be seen.

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
– No
Notes: Supreme high God does not possess hunger.

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
– No
Notes: Nothing is worthy to worship apart from the supreme high God.

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
– Yes [specify]: But are incomprehensible to humans.

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:
– Yes
Notes: Supreme High God communicates to humans through messengers and

prophets.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Notes: Supreme High God communicates to humans through revelation to the messengers in awaking.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: He communicates to some messengers through dreams.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: He communicates to some messengers in trance.

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural High God communicates to some messengers through divination practices.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural High God communicates through messengers and prophets.

↳ Only through monarch

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural High God does not communicate with the monarch unless he is among the prophets or messengers.

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Inspiration.

– Yes

Notes: Supreme High God communicates to humans through messengers and prophets.

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural High God communicates through messengers and prophets.

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit is present at the earliest time.

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– No

Notes: The human spirit is not visible to the eyes.

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: The human spirit cannot be felt physically.

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the world was not available to the human spirit unless when it was descended to Earth.

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not have the power to cause efficacy in the world.

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not have indirect causal efficacy in the world.

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit has a memory of life after the death of its accompanied body.

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: Positive emotions are characteristics of the physical body that are not available to the human spirit.

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: The human spirit does not exhibit negative emotions.

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– Yes

Notes: The human spirit does extend its experiences to the mind of the body through dreams.

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– No

Notes: It only communicates through dreams.

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Notes: It extends messages of experiences through dreams.

↳ In trance possession:

– Yes

Notes: It communicates in trance possession in some rare cases.

↳ Through divination processes:

– No

Notes: The spirit does not communicate through divination processes.

↳ Only through specialists:

– No

Notes: The spirit does not communicate through specialists.

↳ Only through monarch:

– No

Notes: The spirit does not communicate through the monarch.

↳ Communicate with living through other means:

– No

Notes: It only communicates through dreams.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Notes: The non-human supernatural beings are Angels, Jinns, and Devils.

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Notes: Humans could not see these supernatural beings in their true nature.

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– No

Notes: Supernatural beings could not be physically felt, but their presence was established in the writings of the group religion.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Notes: These supernatural beings are aware of this world as Jinns, demons and some Angels are living together with humans in the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Notes: Knowledge of the non-human supernatural being is restricted to some domains of human affairs.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the non-human supernatural being is not restricted within the sampled region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the non-human supernatural being has no restriction within the sampled region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Knowledge of the non-human supernatural being has no restriction outside the sampled region.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see humans everywhere.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings can see humans in the dark.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are not given the power to see what is hidden in the mind of human beings.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings are aware of personal character for living with humans in the same world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings do not know what humans might do in the future.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Non-human supernatural beings are aware of the animals, trees, and other creatures that live in the world.

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings have no power to cause deliberate efficacy in the world.

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Notes: Non-human supernatural beings have no power to cause indirect efficacy of the world.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– No

Notes: Positive emotions of Non-human supernatural beings are not visible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– No

Notes: The invisible nature of non-human supernatural beings renders their negative emotions invisible to humans.

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Notes: Jinns and demons possess hunger, while Angels have no desire for food.

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– Yes [specify]: Demons could instigate humans through a whisper in their minds.

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

Notes: The religious group did not recognize the existence of mixed human-divine beings.

Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The religious group does not possess any supernatural being.

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitoring is agreed upon by the religious group.

There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The group believed that none could be in any place without the accompaniment of angels who record his doings.

Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Notes: The group believed that supernatural monitors record prohibited taboos against the person to have done it.

Food:

– Yes

Notes: Unslaughtered carcasses are among the prohibited food in the principles of the group.

Sacred space(s):

– No

Notes: The group believed angels do not enter the toilet in avoidance of the observance of human nudity.

Sacred object(s):

– No

Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Supernatural beings care about other non-human creatures.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - No
 - Notes: Supernatural monitors among the angels record the killing of coreligionists as a sin against the person.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings among the angels record sin against a person to have killed other religious followers unjustly.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Supernatural beings considered it a sin if the person was killed unjustly.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Angels lack a desire for sex, while Jinns reproduce via sex.

- ↳ Adultery:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Angels who are supernatural monitors record adultery as a sin against the individual.

- ↳ Incest:
 - Yes
 - Notes: In Islam, incest was forbidden, so the angels recorded it as a sin.

- ↳ Other sexual practices:
 - Yes [specify]: Fornication, Sodomy, Lesbianism, etc.
 - Notes: Islam prohibits all of the above, and supernatural monitors record them as sins against a person.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Angels do not lie, while Jinns lie in some prohibited instances.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - Yes
 - Notes: Muslim Jinns are mandated to honor oaths.

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings hate laziness.

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Notes: Sorcery was prohibited by Islam and was thus regarded as an abomination by Muslim Jinns.

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural monitors record it as a sin against a person.

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Notes: Angels support the prohibition of Islam on risks that could negatively impact a person's personality or other attributes.

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Notes: Angels viewed it as good because elders in Islam are expected to be respected.

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Notes: Islam prohibits gossiping and hence was disliked by the angels, while Jinns are expected to avoid it.

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Notes: Islam prohibits property crimes on jinns.

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Notes: Believing jinns (Muslims) are known with proper ritual observance

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Notes: Jinns are commanded to ritual observance on the principles of Islam.

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings considered it good.

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Notes: Jinns are commanded to fairness in economic affairs.

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural beings among jinns cared for their hygiene as an obligation before ritual service.

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Yes [specify]: Humans and Animals

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Notes: Certain angels were created to inflict punishment on the wicked in the Hellfire.

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural punishment is done on the directives of the creator against the wrongdoers.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done by some angels on the directives of the High God.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done by many angels on the orders of the High God.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is done on the command of the High God.

↳ Done by other entities or through other means [specify]

– No

Notes: Angels inflict punishment on evildoers in Hellfire.

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Notes: Disobedience to the directives of the High God is deemed person to punishment.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is reserved to enforce religious adherence.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is reserved to enforce a group of norms commanded by Islam.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is meant to check out selfishness in the mind of believers.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: Those who have violated the tenets of Islamic law are punished.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Notes: The punishment is only done to enforce obedience to the directive of the High God.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The punishment is meted out in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural punishments in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group urged people to obey the principles of Islamic law in order to avoid punishment on the day of judgment.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– No

Notes: The punishment is painful torment in the Hellfire.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: The penalty is harsh.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as an inferior life form:

– No

Notes: The religion of the group rejected the notion of reincarnation.

↳ Punishment in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in an inferior realm:

– No

Notes: The group rejected reincarnation on the principles of Islam.

↳ Other [specify]

– No

Notes: The punishment is done in the Hellfire by burning.

↳ Supernatural punishments are meted out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Some punishments could be indirectly done during the lifetime.

↳ Supernatural punishments in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group highlights some indirect punishments in the lifetime.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck:

– Yes

Notes: Bad luck can be a result of the wrongdoings of evildoers.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of political failure:

– Yes

Notes: Wrongdoers might encounter political failures in life.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of defeat in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Defeat in battle might result from disobedience to the directives of the High God.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of crop failure or bad weather:

– Yes

Notes: Total failure in agriculture and weather might be due to wrongdoings.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of disaster on journeys.

– Yes

Notes: Wrongful acts might lead to a disastrous journey.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of mild sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Sensory displeasure might be part of supernatural punishment in a lifetime.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of extreme sensory displeasure:

– Yes

Notes: Wrongdoers could also experience intense sensory displeasure.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of sickness or illness:

– Yes

Notes: Sickness and illness might be part of supernatural punishment against the wicked.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of impaired reproduction:

– Yes

Notes: Impaired human reproduction could be part of the supernatural punishment.

↳ Punishment in this life consists of bad luck visited on descendants:

– No

Notes: Punishment for the wrongdoings of others might not affect his descendants.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Accidents.

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Notes: Angels record rewards for the person to have done good.

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Notes: Obedience to the directives of the High God attracts reward.

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: The actual reward is only given by High God.

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Notes: The reward could be rendered by angels on the directives of the High God.

↳ Done through impersonal cause-effect principle:

– Yes

Notes: The reward is done without personal effects.

↳ Done to enforce religious ritual-devotional adherence:

– Yes

Notes: The reward is done to encourage people to hold on to ritual devotions.

↳ Done to enforce group norms:

– Yes

Notes: The reward is granted to encourage people on good character.

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– Yes

Notes: The reward is granted to wipe out selfishness in the mind of people.

↳ Done randomly:

– No

Notes: The reward is done systematically.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in the afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: The actual benefit of the reward is given in the afterlife.

↳ Supernatural rewards in the afterlife are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group advocates rewards in the afterlife.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Mild sensory pleasure is among the reward in the afterlife.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: The reward in the afterlife consists of extreme pleasure.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of eternal happiness:

– Yes

Notes: Reward in the afterlife encompasses eternal happiness.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation as a superior life form:

– No

Notes: The principles of the group's religion had not recognized incarnation.

↳ Reward in the afterlife consists of reincarnation in a superior realm:

– No

Notes: The group dismissed the idea of reincarnation.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: Many wives.

↳ Supernatural rewards are bestowed out in this lifetime:

– Yes

Notes: Supernatural rewards could be received in a lifetime.

↳ Supernatural rewards in this life are highly emphasized by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group emphasized supernatural rewards in the lifetime.

↳ Reward in this life consists of good luck:

– Yes

Notes: Good luck could be part of the supernatural reward.

↳ Reward in this life consists of political success or power:

– Yes

Notes: Political success and power could be part of the reward in this life.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success in battle:

– Yes

Notes: Success on the battlefield could be counted among the reward.

↳ Reward in this life consists of peace or social stability:

– Yes

Notes: Peace and stability in life could indirectly be among the reward of good deeds.

↳ Reward in this life consists of healthy crops or good weather:

– Yes

Notes: A better yield at farm could be among the reward.

↳ Reward in this life consists of success on journeys:

– Yes

Notes: A successful journey could be enlisted among the reward of good deeds in the world.

↳ Reward in this life consists of mild sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Sensory pleasure and happiness could be counted among the rewards of doing good things in this world.

↳ Reward in this life consists of extreme sensory pleasure:

– Yes

Notes: Sensory pleasure might be among the rewards of good deeds in the world.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced health:

– Yes

Notes: Enhanced health of a person might be considered among his reward for good deeds in the world.

↳ Reward in this life consists of enhanced reproductive success:

– Yes

Notes: An enhanced reproductive success might be counted among the reward.

↳ Reward in this life consists of fortune visited on descendants:

– Yes

Notes: A series of fortuneds could be among the reward of good deeds in the world.

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: General success.

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Notes: The group believed in Mahadi as messier.

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Notes: The messier will appear towards the end of the world.

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Notes: The purpose of a messier appearance is to save people from the dilemma.

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The religion of the group had prescribed social norms for people to adopt.

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Notes: The group had not made a distinction between the conventional and moral norms.

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: The group had rejected celibacy.

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: Members of the group have no restrictions on lawful sex.

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Notes: The group has rejected castration.

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group are required to fast during the month of Ramadan.

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Notes: Members of the group are not restricted on food except what is prohibited by the religion of Islam.

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Notes: Membership of the group does not require permanent scarring.

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Notes: Membership of the group does not require painful wounds.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Notes: The group prohibits the sacrifice of adults.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

— No

Notes: The group prohibits the sacrifice of children.

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

— No

Notes: The religion of the group prohibits suicide.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

— No

Notes: Membership in the group does not require a sacrifice of properties.

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

— Yes

Notes: Members of the group are recommended to attend the chanting of praises to the prophet Muhammad (SAW).

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

— No

Notes: Membership in the group does not require taking physical risks.

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

— Yes

Notes: Members of the group are required to accept the Islamic precepts.

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

— No

Notes: Members of the group accept out-group members.

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

— Yes

Notes: Members are recommended to attend the weekly chanting of prases to the prophet

MuhamMad (SAW).

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):
Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Hours: 168

Notes: weekly

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Notes: Members of the group are recommended to attend annual Maulud festivals to praise the Prophet (SAW).

↳ On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Number of participants: 100000

Notes: Members of the group from various locations attend the celebration.

↳ What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Average interval [hours]: 8760

Notes: The occasion occurs annually.

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Notes: The celebration is expected to be done morally on the principles of Islam.

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Notes: Both the annual and weekly praises are organized on designated principles of Islam.

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Yes

Notes: The praises are done on the stanzas of some selected books.

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Notes: Use of intoxicants is prohibited on these occasions.

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Notes: The group membership does not require a special appearance apart from the Islamic system of dress and practices.

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Notes: The group did not employ fictive kinship terminology in their practices.

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Notes: The group belong the the Islamic state.

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Notes: The group does not provide additional aid beyond the obligatory charity (Zakat).

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Both obligatory and voluntary charity (Zakat and Sadaqat) are available to the poor members of the group.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: The group members do not have to provide institutionalized poverty relief apart from Zakat and Sadaqat.

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Group members are entitled to receive zakat from the rest of the Muslims.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Notes: It is recommended that group members provide care to those who are weak, especially children and elderly people.

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Weak members among the elderly and infirm are entitled to receive support from their fellow Muslims.

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group established educational sessions for its members to upgrade their scholarly standards.

Is formal education restricted to religious professionals:

– No

Notes: Formal education is meant for the entire members.

Is such education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: The education is open to both male and female sexes.

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Notes: The group members have access to whatever Islamic educational institution within the caliphate.

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Notes: Both sexes have access to extra-religious education within the state.

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the organization have access to the bureaucracy of the group.

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Notes: Any bureaucrat outside their organization is free to interact with the group members.

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

— No

Notes: The group did not make any provision for public food facilities to the members of the caliphate.

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— No

Notes: Group members of the organization engage in various economic activities to earn livelihood apart from much reliance on other institutional provisions.

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

— No

Notes: The religious group did not participate in water management with members or members of other institutions.

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The bureaucrats of the caliphate ensure water management for the organizational members.

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

— No

Notes: The religious group did not establish a separate transportation system for the group members.

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The government of the province ensures transportation infrastructure for every member of the region.

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

— Yes

Notes: The religious group can manage the organization's affairs through monthly contributions from its members.

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

— Yes

Notes: The administrative body of the caliphate typically levies taxes on the members of the organization.

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Notes: The religious group did not precisely provide an institutionalized police force to the organization or the caliphate.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group's members openly interact with a security force established by the caliphate of the region.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Notes: The organization relied on the judiciary system established by the caliphate.

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The organization's operations relied on the judiciary system established by the administrative body of the region.

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Notes: Institutionalized punishment is only administered by the authoritative judges of the region.

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group members are subjected to any punishment institutionalized by the administrative body of the region.

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Notes: Once sentenced through the provision of the shari'ah.

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Notes: Once necessary.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Notes: The member could be subjected to corporal punishment on the adjudication of a shari'ah judge.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– Yes

Notes: Members of the organization could be sentenced to ostracism once decided by a shari'ah judge.

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Notes: The region's institutionalized judicial system could seize any member's property.

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Notes: The religious group stuck to the formal code of the Islamic shari'ah.

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Group members are subjected to the legal codes established by Islam under the region.

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Notes: The religious group did not have an institutionalized military force within the region.

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: They might participate in any military campaign organized by the caliphate of the region.

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group is subjected to the protection of the military force established by the caliphate of the region.

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: The religious group utilized the Arabic language in the provision of Islam.

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group communicates in Hausa, Fulfulde, and English in addition to Arabic language.

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The group utilizes other formal languages of the region, especially English and Hausa.

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group utilizes the Islamic lunar calendar while scheduling their occasions.

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: Islam established the calendar used by the group.

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: The religious group relied on their menace of earning to provide food for themselves.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Notes: The group relied on their efforts to provide food for themselves.

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